

The Distribution of Gender Wage Discrimination in Italy and Spain: A Comparison Using the ECHP

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Purpose of this paper

In this paper we focus on the individual distribution of gender wage discrimination in Spain and Italy, relying upon the development of Jenkins' (1994) distributional approach proposed in Del Rio et al. (2006).

Design/methodology/approach

We estimate the degree of individual discrimination for each employed woman and, relying on the decomposability properties of these estimates, we assess the nature and extent of discrimination across various socio-economic groupings.

Findings

We find that some mechanisms inhibit the access of highly educated women to highly rewarding occupations in Italy, especially in the public sector, but not in Spain.

Research limitations/implications

The treatment of occupation and sector of activity has some impact on our results, shedding doubts on the robustness of some previous analyses of discrimination in these countries.

Practical implications

While no doubt the appraisal of the glass ceiling in the Italian labour market will gain extensively from further research, we find some prima-facie evidence highlighting the role of appointment and promotion procedures.

What is original/value of paper

A remarkable institutional divide characterises Spain and Italy in the domain of gender wage discrimination. A powerful political pressure along the lines of gender quotas for public employment has long been in place in Spain, while nothing of the kind existed in Italy.

Keywords Gender wage discrimination, distributive analysis, glass ceiling

JEL: J16, J31, J71

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Introduction

There is perhaps no more socially controversial issue in economics than the perceived existence of earning discrimination.¹ This discrimination occurs when a feature, such as race or gender, has no influence on the ability of an employee to perform a given activity, and yet employers base their hiring and pay decisions on the employee's race or gender. The existence of significant gender wage gaps is a recurrent feature of labour markets in a very large number of countries. Female employees consistently get lower remuneration for their work than their male colleagues. The extent to which this gap can be attributed to discriminatory practices among employers is a key question that can be addressed from different perspectives. Among the latter, the Oaxaca-Blinder (OB) decomposition has been of paramount importance. This procedure decomposes the observed (raw) wage gap into a component ascribable to the observable characteristics of the workforce and a component unexplained by these observable characteristics, interpreted as the effect of wage discrimination. Accordingly, throughout this paper we mean by discrimination the wage gap attributable to differences in rewards unexplained by observable characteristics.

The OB decomposition has been applied many times to obtain aggregate measures of gender wage discrimination, using different data sources from various countries. However, cross-country measurements are relatively rare, due to the difficulty of finding comparable data sources among different countries. The OB decomposition, moreover, does not yield any insight about the distribution of gender wage gaps (and discrimination) across different subgroups of female workers. Indeed, aggregate measures may hide important features that can be revealed by looking at the distribution (among individuals or among intermediate-level groups) of the discrimination measures. Accordingly, various recent contributions have modified the traditional OB framework in order to allow for distributional aspects in the study of gender wage discrimination. In particular, Machado and Mata (2005) construct counterfactual female wage distributions based upon quantile regressions (Koenker and Bassett, 1978). All these approaches, however, suffer, from an important drawback: they rely on the comparison between estimated and counterfactual wages either at the mean or quantile by quantile. As a consequence, they are unable to shed light on the individual dimension of the wage gap due to observable characteristics, and they may

¹ It is perhaps worth recalling at this juncture that the first law signed by President Obama has been the Lilly Ledbetter Fair Pay Restoration Act, making it easier for workers to sue for pay discrimination.

produce misleading results when the differences between the estimated and counterfactual distributions depend not only on the discrimination suffered by individuals but also on the mobility across the wage distribution. Besides, the quantile-regression approach assumes that the non-discriminatory wage structure (depending upon characteristics such as education, experience, and so on) changes across the wage distribution without any a priori presumption about the pattern of these variations. Hence, discrimination varies across the wage distribution. It is however not usually made clear a priori why a given characteristic should have different rewards in different parts of the wage distribution.² These issues were addressed by Jenkins (1994), who proposed a distributional approach to wage discrimination both identifying individual measures of discrimination and summing up these individual measures through an index endowed with a set of desirable properties.

In this paper we focus on the individual distribution of gender wage discrimination, relying upon a development of Jenkins' distributional approach proposed in Del Rio et al. (2006). We first estimate the degree of individual discrimination for each employed woman, then proceeding to aggregate these individual measures across different socio-economic groupings, and to compare some features of the resultant subgroup distributions. We select for our analysis two particular EU countries, Italy and Spain, because their labour markets share some general similarities and because their aggregate measures of discrimination (according to European Community Household Panel -ECHP- data) are pretty close. Moreover, the distribution of wage discrimination across different groups of Spanish female workers has recently drawn some attention in the literature (we refer in particular to De la Rica et al., 2008). Hence the interest of applying the distributional approach to both Spain and an apparently similar country, Italy, in order to see whether a similar story can be told in both cases. Indeed, our analysis reveals significant differences in the distribution of the Italian and Spanish individual measures of discrimination that would be very hard to detect from more aggregate results. In particular, we find that some mechanisms inhibit the access of highly educated women to highly rewarding occupations in Italy, especially in the public sector, but not in Spain. We also find that the treatment of occupation and industry³ has some impact on our results, shedding some doubts on the robustness of the

² Indeed, it is usually believed that the very position of the wage distribution occupied by a given individual is determined by her/his characteristics

³ Throughout this paper, industries are the NACE sectors of activity, while the term of sector is used to distinguish the private from the public sector.

results obtained in De la Rica et al. (2008) and in the subsequent literature.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows. In Section 1 we place our analysis within the gender wage discrimination literature, arguing in greater detail why further knowledge about wage distributions in Italy and Spain may be of general interest. Section 2 gives some information about the features of ECHP, the variables we use, and their definitions. In Section 3 we apply the standard OB decomposition to obtain aggregate measures of the degree of gender wage discrimination for Italy and Spain. We then illustrate the distributional approach to gender wage gaps proposed in Del Rio et al. (2006), and describe a family of discrimination indexes consistent with this approach. In Section 4, various indexes of discrimination are then computed for different groupings (by educational level, occupation and industry) of female employees. This allows us to show how discrimination changes across these subgroups in Italy and Spain, and to provide an interpretation of these findings. Finally, we offer some concluding remarks.

Glass Ceilings, Sticky Floors and Sticky Doors

Blau and Kahn (1992, 1996, and 2003) are the first authors that have investigated the gender wage gap through cross-country analysis, relying on micro data from the International Social Survey Programme (ISSP). They are mainly interested about the impact of aggregate wage inequality and wage-setting institutions upon gender wage discrimination. In the 1992 and 1996 papers they find that a more compressed (male) wage structure reduces significantly discrimination. In the 2003 paper they also find that female labour supply is positively correlated to discrimination, and that the latter is reduced by stronger collective bargaining.⁴ Weichselbaumer and Winter-Ebmer (2007) evaluate the impact of economic and legal variables on gender wage discrimination. They use a cross-country data set constructed through a meta-analysis of previous studies. Their results show that discrimination is reduced by both more competitive markets and stricter equal treatment laws. Olivetti and Petrongolo (2008), using the PSID data for the US and ECHP data for European countries, analyse the negative correlation of gender wage and employment gaps across countries, arguing that, if women who are employed tend to have relatively high-wage

⁴ Blau and Kahn (1992, 1996) measure discrimination through the Juhn-Murphy-Pierce decomposition, while Blau and Kahn (2003) adopt a different indicator (the gender wage gap predicted on the assumption that men and women in each country and year have the same mean levels of observable characteristics as US men and women for that year).

characteristics, low female employment rates may become consistent with low gender wage gaps simply because low-wage women would not feature in the observed wage distribution. Olivetti and Petrongolo recover information on wages for the non employed using alternative imputation techniques, and find that, having corrected for lower participation rates, the raw wage gap in Ireland and southern Europe widens to similar levels to those of other European countries and the US. However, selection of women into work is strongly associated to human capital and observable job characteristics, implying that its impact is much smaller on the wage gap component unexplained by differences in observable characteristics (that is, discrimination).

Other cross-country studies relying upon the ECHP data set are Rice (1999), who adopted the Juhn-Murphy-Pierce decomposition to obtain an aggregate discrimination levels for each country, Barth et al. (2002) and European Commission (2002), relying upon the traditional OB decomposition. Very little work on the cross-country gender wage gap has been taking into account the whole wage distribution: none of the previously quoted analyses can grasp the extent of the gender gap at different points of the wage distribution. The main exception to this is Arulampalam et al. (2007), where the variation of the gender wage gap across the wage distribution is investigated using ECHP data within the quantile regression framework. Arulampalam et al. (2007) find an unequal incidence along the wage distribution of the wage gap component unexplained by differences in observable characteristics. Moreover, in Italy, as well as in most of the analysed countries, this component behaves differently between private and public sectors. In the public sector female workers experience higher differences in rewards only at the top of the distribution (the so-called glass-ceiling effect). On the contrary, a higher unexplained proportion of the wage gap is estimated at both extremes of the private sector wage distribution (the glass ceiling is accompanied by what they label a sticky floor). In addition, there is evidence that countries with more unequal wage distributions - like the UK, Ireland and Spain - have larger mean gender gaps, even wider sticky floors, but less pronounced glass ceilings.

A study that has drawn considerable attention is De la Rica et al. (2008). They analyse the gender wage gap throughout the wage distribution in Spain using ECHP data for 1999, stratifying their sample by education group and using quantile regression and panel data techniques. They find that, in line with the conventional glass-ceiling effect, the wage gap increases as one moves up the wage distribution of highly educated

workers. However, for less-educated workers the contrary happens. De la Rica et al. (2008) argue that this sticky-floor (or glass-ceiling-at-the-ground-floor, as dubbed by these authors) pattern can be explained by statistical discrimination exerted by employers in countries where less educated women have low participation rates.⁵ As the careers of (especially less educated) women may suffer from frequent interruptions - due to societal discrimination in family duties, lack of family aid policies, or religious beliefs - employers may use statistical discrimination to pay a lower proportion of the training cost for women than for men. This phenomenon brings about lower female wages at entry jobs (in the lower part of the wage distribution), with the reasons behind statistical discrimination vanishing as job tenure expands.

In Italy, Addabbo and Favaro (2007) use data from the 2001 wave of the ECHP to evaluate the extension of the wage gap due to differences in rewards at different points of the distribution of female earnings, conditioning on the educational level. Using a quantile regression estimation procedure, they find results similar to those in De la Rica et al. (2008). Females with an educational level lower than upper-secondary school diploma experience the highest levels of wage discrimination in the left-hand part of the wage distribution; as the wage increases, the amount of discrimination decreases (sticky-floor effect). On the other hand, there is some evidence of a glass-ceiling pattern among highly educated females. They also find that, across the whole distribution, highly educated women suffer a lower unexplained wage gap than their less educated colleagues.

All the above contributions, being based, at most, on quantile-by-quantile comparisons between estimated and counterfactual wage distributions, are unable to shed light on the individual dimension of the wage gap. There are some however some recent contributions closely related to our approach. Del Rio et al. (2006) use Spanish data for 1995 (from the Encuesta de Estructura Salarial -Survey of Wage Structure-undertaken by the Instituto Nacional de Estadística) and analyse discriminatory individual discrimination according to the methodology that we present below in greater detail. They find significantly higher relative discrimination levels for women with very low wages, and this pattern is repeated for women holding less than a university degree. On the other hand, females workers holding a university degree experience higher relative discrimination levels when earning the highest wages, as was found by De la

⁵ We note for future reference that this is not a sample selection argument. De la Rica et al. (2007) argue that non random selection into work is irrelevant for the pattern of wage discrimination.

Rica et al. (2008). Both sticky floors and glass ceilings then seem to exist in the Spanish labour market, with the former being quantitatively stronger.

Favaro and Magrini (2008) study the distribution of the wage gap among young workers in North-eastern Italy (using administrative data from the National Institute of Social Security). Also following the methodological suggestions of Jenkins (1994), they develop a non parametric estimation of the discrimination experienced by each female worker,⁶ and find that the discriminatory component of the wage gap has been increasing through the 1990s across the whole distribution, but it has been more accentuated for females earning the highest wages. Therefore, a glass ceiling effect seems to have been emerging through the last decade. Moreover, highly educated women suffer, in general, less discrimination than less educated females but experience much higher gaps on moving towards the top of the distribution. In addition, longer labour market experience and firm tenure do not help reduce the wage gap.

Addabbo et al. (2007) study wage differentials between male and female workers in Italy, using data from the 2001 wave of the ECHP. Unlike Favaro and Magrini (2008), who rely on OLS estimation, they employ the quantile regression analysis to derive marginal distributions from estimated values. Once again, their results indicate a sticky-floor pattern for highly educated women and a glass-ceiling pattern for highly educated female workers. Moreover, highly educated women experience lower wage gaps compared to their less educated colleagues. Addabbo et al. (2007) also find that education interacts differently with other human capital characteristics. Less educated women tendentially suffer lower wage discrimination when achieving longer labour market experience and firm tenure. On the contrary, as the latter variables increase, gender discrimination for highly educated females worsens.

A striking feature of the literature that has followed in the wake of the De la Rica et al. (2008) is the relative lack of attention for the impact of industry upon the level and pattern of wage discrimination. De la Rica et al. (2008), as well as Del Rio et al. (2006), only include a dummy for the public sector (recall that the data used by Del Rio et al., 2006), do not cover Agriculture, Public Administration, Health Services and Education). Addabbo and Favaro (2007), and Addabbo et al. (2007) include dummies for agriculture, services and public sector. Only Favaro and Magrini (2008) include

⁶ This non parametric method consists in measuring the incidence of the wage gap at the individual level, and then in estimating the conditional bivariate density functions defined on the individual levels of the gap and the corresponding individual characteristics.

two-digit industry dummies (their data, however, do not cover Agriculture, Public Administration, Health Services and Education).

Hence, the degree of attention paid to sectoral disaggregation across these studies is generally low, and none of them fully allows either for behavioural changes across private and public sectors, or for the possibility that results are driven by compositional effects across these sectors. However, it is often recognised in the literature that sexist prejudices are stronger in the private sector and that gender wage discrimination should be analysed separately for the public and private sector (see for instance Arulampalam et al., 2007). Otherwise, sticky floors may just be the result of a composition effect, with women having relatively low paying jobs in the private sector and relatively higher paying jobs in the public sector.

More generally, it is clear that the analysis of gender wage discrimination across the wage distribution must be couched within a careful treatment of sectoral and occupational differences. Glass ceilings are understood to reveal the inequitable rationing of “good” jobs in short supply. Women may then have wage distributions which look similar to male ones over ordinary jobs, but are comparatively thin over high-paying jobs. A similar explanation applies to sticky floors, which can occur because of labour market segmentation, with barriers against access to good (or even ordinary) jobs for women. In this sense, it has been suggested (Gunewardena et al., 2009) that sticky floors (as well as glass ceilings) may actually be “sticky doors”, that is barriers against access to “good” industries or occupations for disadvantaged groups.

Glass ceilings and sticky floors may obviously occur also because of other reasons. A typical justification for glass ceilings is taste-based (see, for instance, Albrecht et al., 2003). Women would prefer to work in family-friendly jobs, not committing strongly to a career, because of parental leave policies and day care systems not providing enough incentives to work participation. Another explanation is based upon the model by Lazear and Rosen (1990). As women have higher domestic productivity, employers are reluctant to invest in their training on an equal basis with men.

Sticky floors may occur because of statistical discrimination, as explained in De la Rica et al. (2008). Also, women at the bottom of the distribution have less bargaining power compared to men due to family commitments or social custom, also meaning that

they are often appointed at a lower starting wage within a particular career (Arulampalam et al., 2007). Even in regulated labour markets with anti-discrimination legislation, only the more articulate and better educated are willing to take legal action against breaches of the law.

At any rate, a careful assessment of these arguments calls for a careful treatment of sectoral and occupational differences. The distributional approach to wage discrimination is particularly suited to this kind of exercise. In this paper we apply it to the analysis of gender wage discrimination in Spain, that has elicited considerable interest after the study by De la Rica et al. (2008). Spain is contrasted with Italy, with which it shares some general similarities in the labour market structure and in the aggregate measures of discrimination. As will be seen below, the distributional approach reveals some interesting differences in the distribution of the Italian and Spanish individual measures of discrimination across occupations and industries.

Data Source and Variables

The data source used in this paper is the ECHP elaborated by Eurostat. This is a harmonised, large-scale, cross-national longitudinal survey conducted annually from 1994 to 2001. ECHP is a survey based on a standardised questionnaire that involves annual interviewing of a representative panel of households and individuals in each country, covering a wide range of topics: income, health, education, housing, demographic and employment characteristics, etc. The variables included in ECHP are appropriate for cross-country comparisons due to the standardised design of the survey and the common technical and implementation procedures carried out with centralised support and coordination of the national surveys by Eurostat.

Our analysis will be carried for the period 1997 to 2001 (waves 4 to 8 of ECHP). Wave 1 does not include information about the type of contract. Waves 2 and 3 suffer, both for Italy and Spain, from a large number of missing answers relating to the size of the firm where the individual was employed at the time of the survey. As we consider both type of contract and firm size to be relevant for the analysis of gender wage discrimination, we restrict our sample to a shorter period. Table A1 in the Appendix shows some descriptive statistics of the sample we used.

Compared with other European social surveys, ECHP presents a much broader

and integrative character. For our purposes it is important to notice that ECHP improves upon Italian national data as far as work-hours are concerned (in Italy, most of the research upon hourly wages has to rely on rather rough approximations; see on this Addabbo et al., 2007). However, ECHP lacks detailed information about the structure of wage earnings, like basic rates of pay, overtime remuneration, bonuses, etc. ⁷ Besides, ECHP is a household survey, lacking in matched employer-employee information. This may result in measurement errors due to interviewed persons overstating or understating their wages. A third problem is the lack of information about actual work experience. In order to overcome this weakness, we have computed a measure of potential experience as the difference between the current age of the individual minus the age at which he/she started his/her first job.

Our key variable in the analysis of the gender wage gap is the hourly wage computed as gross average monthly earnings from the main job (including bonuses and overtime) divided by weekly hours in the main job (including overtime) times (12/52). As indicated above, ECHP does not provide detailed information about overtime hours or premia. We set an upper bound of 60 hours to the work-hours variable to minimise the bias due to overstatements in self-declared hours, as in De la Rica et al. (2008). Nominal wages have been deflated using EU harmonised indexes of consumer prices (HICP).

Gender Wage Discrimination in Italy and Spain

A preliminary illustration of the (raw) gender gap on our data is provided by means of the plots in Figure 1, depicting, for the 1997-2001 period, the differences of logged gross hourly wages of male and female full-time workers in Spain and Italy throughout the wage distribution, together with the mean gap (horizontal line). Like in De la Rica et al. (2008) we consider separately workers with tertiary education and other workers.

⁷ The European Structure of Earnings Survey (ESES) contains detailed information about wages. Its reliability is relatively high because it is an employer's survey, and its sample size is larger. However, it excludes the public sector and it is carried out infrequently. For a comparison between ECHP and ESES related to gender wage gaps see Barry et al. (2001).

Figure 1: Raw gender wage gap (full-time workers; pooled 1997-2001 ECHP waves)

Indeed, we get a picture of the gender gap very similar to the one in De la Rica et al. (2008) for the 1999 wave of the ECHP. The gap for the highly educated workers in both countries chimes in with the conventional glass-ceiling shape, in stark contrast with the decreasing (sticky-floor) pattern for the less educated workers. We saw in Section 2 that De la Rica et al. (2008) provide several explanations for these phenomena. In this paper, we examine them through a distributional approach, allowing the computation of decomposable indexes of discrimination. We shall see that most of the sticky-floor pattern, as well as the strong similarity between Italy and Spain and the stark contrast between highly and less educated workers in the latter country, largely vanish once proper care is taken of differences across occupations and industries (in particular, when private and public sectors are analysed separately).

As a first step we compute aggregate measures of the degree of wage discrimination following the OB procedure. Thus, we estimate the following Mincerian wage equations - separately for each country and for male and female employees - on a pool comprising waves 4 to 8 (both inclusive) of the ECHP:

$$\log w_i = Z_i' \hat{\beta} + u_i \quad (1)$$

where i stands for each individual employee, w_i for his/her (real) hourly wage, Z_i' represents a vector of individual characteristics considered to be linked to productivity (including a dummy variable for each year in the sample, intended to catch time-related effects),⁸ $\hat{\beta}$ the vector of estimated coefficients, and u_i the error terms. The estimation results are presented in Table A2 of the Appendix.

The OB measure of wage discrimination is computed taking as a benchmark (the non-discriminatory ideal situation) the wage structure of male employees.⁹ The wage gap (in logs) can be decomposed as:

$$\log \{ \bar{w}_M - \log \{ \bar{w}_F = (\bar{Z}'_M - \bar{Z}'_F) \hat{\beta}_M + (\hat{\beta}_M - \hat{\beta}_F) \bar{Z}'_F \} \quad (1)$$

where the bar over a variable indicates its average value over the sample and subscripts M and F stand for male and female, respectively. The first term of this decomposition shows the part of the wage gap that can be attributed to average differences in individual characteristics between both groups (the “endowment effect”). The second term, instead, shows the part that can be attributed to differences in the valuation of each characteristic between both groups. These differences in valuation are obtained as a residual that cannot be explained appealing to individual characteristics, and so they are usually identified as the result of gender discrimination.

Note that in this paper we do not allow for the impact of non random selection into work upon the pattern of wage discrimination. From the analyses of De la Rica et al. (2008) and Olivetti and Petrongolo (2008), one can surmise that allowing for non random selection is not likely to make a sizeable difference in our results. We ran indeed our Mincerian wage equations with a standard Heckman correction for selectivity bias (a procedure which is fraught with some important conceptual difficulties in the interpretation of the results as far as discrimination is concerned, see

⁸ This decomposition method assumes that the variables in Z are not affected themselves by discrimination and that they measure productivity comprehensively. Regarding this last point, if there were any relevant variables not included in Z correlated with gender, the residual obtained as a result could be capturing unobserved group differences in productivity, like e.g. those arising from voluntary choices made by women. The variables included in Z are listed in the Appendix, Table A1.

⁹ Oaxaca (1973) noted that the choice of a benchmark wage structure is subjected to the well-known “index number problem”. Neumark (1988) pointed out that the choice hinges on the type of behaviour under analysis (discrimination or nepotism). To take the male wage structure as a benchmark implies to assume that discriminatory behaviour is exclusively directed against women, not in favour of men.

Neuman and Oaxaca, 2004) and did not find appreciably different results from those reported in the text. These equations are available upon request.

Table 1 shows the aggregated results for Italy and Spain. While the average wage gap during the period was almost double in Spain than in Italy, the respective degrees of discrimination were much more similar, and close to the EU average.¹⁰

Table 1 – Measuring Gender Wage Discrimination through the OB Decomposition

	W_f/W_m	W_f/W_m (in absence of discrimination)	Wage gap due to different characteristics	Discrimination
<i>Italy</i>	93.14%	104.83%	-4.83%	11.69%
<i>Spain</i>	86.49%	102.06%	-2.06%	15.57%

Both in Italy and Spain, furthermore, the average characteristics of the female employees would bring about, in non discriminatory conditions, a favourable wage gap for them against their male colleagues. Similarity in aggregate measures can however hide significant differences at lower levels of aggregation. To see this, we consider the distribution of discrimination throughout the wage structure, relying on the approach proposed in Del Rio et al. (2006). This methodology is intrinsically more flexible than either the traditional OB, or the quantile-regression approach, because it considers the whole wage distribution rather than the mean or a few given quantiles.¹¹ Then, relying on the decomposability properties of these indexes, the discrimination indexes are aggregated across various socio-economic groupings, allowing us to assess empirically the nature and extent of discrimination across these groups. Moreover, as we shall see below, we can make various hypotheses about the non discriminatory reward structure.

Another important point is that we will rely on a relative measure of individual discrimination. For each woman we compute her degree of discrimination vis-à-vis her counterfactual wage in absence of discrimination. The relative nature of this measure makes cross-unit, including cross-country, comparisons possible.

¹⁰ The European Commission (2002) estimates (on data from the ECHP, year 1998) for Italy and Spain a discrimination of respectively 9 and 17 percentage points (13 points for the European area). This compares to median values of respectively 17.5 and 19 points from the studies reviewed in Commission of the European Communities (2003)

¹¹ The computation of the indexes proposed in Del Rio et al. (2006) can in principle be grafted either on OLS or on quantile-regression estimates. Here, to provide a clearer illustration of the methodology and its novelty, we graft it on OLS. As shown in Del Rio et al. (2006), either choice is not likely to provide appreciably different results.

In order to obtain individual measures of the degree of discrimination, we compute for each female employee the difference between her estimated wage if her individual characteristics were remunerated at average male rewards (r_{Fi}) and her estimated wage if her individual characteristics were remunerated at average female rewards (y_{Fi}).¹² We define the measure of the individual degree of discrimination, following Del Rio et al. (2006) as:

$$v_{Fi} = \left(\frac{r_{Fi} - y_{Fi}}{r_{Fi}} \right) \quad (1)$$

The information thus obtained about the distribution of discrimination could be represented through a simple graphical device (derived by Del Rio et al., 2006, from the General Normalised Inverse Lorenz Curve and called the discrimination curve). Here, however, in order to get a more precise picture of the distribution of the degree of discrimination we compute the following indexes, also proposed by Del Rio et al. (2006), based on the family of poverty indexes developed by Foster et al. (1984):

$$dr_{\alpha}(v_{Fi}) = \left(\frac{1}{n} \right)^{k^* i (v_{Fi})^{\alpha}} \sum_{i=1}^{k^* i} i \quad (1)$$

where α would represent a coefficient of “aversion to discrimination”, greater when a greater weight is put on the most discriminated female employees, and k^* stands for the number of discriminated female employees.

We compute the indexes corresponding to values of α equal to 0, 1 and 2. Index dr_0 simply shows the percentage of female employees that suffer wage discrimination, no matter the extent of it. We take it as an indicator of the “diffusion” of discrimination among female employees. Index dr_1 , if applied to the whole group, would give us the same value as the aggregate measure of discrimination obtained through the OB decomposition if we computed this decomposition eliminating all instances of positive discrimination towards female employees. We take it as an indicator of the “intensity” of the discrimination suffered in average by female employees. Index dr_2 assigns greater weights to female employees that suffer higher degrees of discrimination. We interpret

¹² Rewards for characteristics are obtained as $r_{Fi} = \exp(Z_{Fi} \hat{\beta}_M)$; $y_{Fi} = \exp(Z_{Fi} \hat{\beta}_F)$. As already said, an alternative approach would be to use quantile regression methods, that allow for the possibility that characteristics may have different returns at different points of the distribution.

it as an indicator of the “severity” of discrimination, i.e. we consider as more severe or worrying a situation where discrimination measured by dr_2 is higher.¹³

Table 2 shows the aggregated values of the indexes for both countries. While the percentage of discriminated female employees is slightly higher in Italy than in Spain, consistently with the above OB decomposition, the aggregate degree of wage discrimination is higher in Spain. The values of index dr_2 confirm that discrimination is more severe for Spanish female employees.

Table 1: Discrimination indexes

	dr_0	dr_1	dr_2
Italy	97.15%	11.30%	1.55%
Spain	95.75%	15.10%	2.94%

In order to compare the relative evenness of the distribution of discrimination between Italy and Spain we compute, for each group, the relative ratio between the dr_2 values in both countries.¹⁴ To compensate for the differences in the average measures of discrimination, we detract from this ratio the ratio between the correspondent dr_1 indexes squared:

$$\gamma = \frac{dr_2^S}{dr_2^I} - \left(\frac{dr_1^S}{dr_1^I} \right)^2 \quad (1)$$

where the superscripts S, I stand for Spain and Italy, respectively. The value of γ will be zero when the relative ratio between the dr_2 indexes takes exactly the value correspondent to the differences in the average measures of discrimination in both countries. Thus, values greater than zero indicate a more uneven distribution of discrimination for Spanish female employees. In our case, the value of γ turns out to be positive (0.10), giving additional confirmation that the distribution of the individual measures of the degree of discrimination is more uneven for the Spanish data.

As we shall see in the following section, however, the real advantage of the

¹³ As was pointed by Del Rio et al. (2006), this introduces a normative dimension to the index that is not present in the case of dr_0 or dr_1 . The weights the index dr_2 use incorporate the value judgment that discrimination is a “bad thing”, of which it would be better to have less.

¹⁴ Note that dr_2 conflates two different dimensions of discrimination. If we compare two groups of female employees with the same average level of discrimination as indicated by dr_1 , that with the most uneven distribution of the individual degrees of discrimination will show a higher dr_2 . Alternatively, if we compare two groups of female employees with a similar distribution of the individual degrees of discrimination but different average levels, that with the higher average level will show a higher value for dr_2 .

indexes proposed by Del Rio et al. (2006) lies in their decomposability, which allows their computation for different socio-economic groupings. This is of great importance for the incorporation of sectoral and occupational differences within the analysis of wage discrimination.

The Distribution of the Degree of Discrimination among Different Groupings

It was already made clear by Jenkins (1994) that the interest of a distributional approach to wage discrimination lies not only in the identification of individual measures of discrimination, but also in their meaningful aggregation through indexes endowed with desirable properties. We now propose to demonstrate this on the Italian and Spanish ECHP data. The decomposability of the indexes developed by Del Rio et al. (2006) leads to an accurate assessment of the relationships between sector, industry, occupation, and gender wage discrimination, shedding some novel light on the glass-ceiling and sticky-floor phenomena found in the literature.

In the first place, we compute the values of the indexes by educational levels. The detailed results can be found in Table A3 (in the Appendix). Figure 2 shows the values of dr_2 for the three educational groups we can distinguish in our sample. We can observe that the severity of discrimination is higher for Spanish female employees in every group. Its profile across educational groups is, however, very similar, being highest for the less educated female employees, and lowest for the intermediate group, comprising female employees with upper secondary studies.

Figure 1: Values of dr_2 for educational levels

Note: see the Legend in the Appendix for a full explanation of the acronyms and other terms.

These results are consistent with the existence of both a glass-ceiling and sticky-floor effect in our data (as in Del Rio et al., 2006, the latter seems however stronger). To gain further insight upon this matter, let us now group workers according to the industries where they are employed. Figure 3 shows the correspondent values of dr_2 (detailed results are reported in Table A4). We observe that, again, the severity of the distribution of discrimination in Spain is higher in most industries. Only in one of them (Education), the severity of discrimination is higher in Italy. What the graph shows clearly is that the relative severity of discrimination between industries cuts a different profile in each country. In Spain, discrimination is most severe for female employees in Construction and the Household and other services industries, while in Italy this is the case for the Primary activities and Energy sector (Construction also showing a high relative value of dr_2). On the other side, discrimination is less severe for Italian female employees in Health and Public Administration, while in Spain the less discriminated are the female employees in Education. There is then evidence of a different distribution of discrimination in the public and the private sector. Below we build upon this insight.

Figure 1: Values of dr_2 for industries

Note: see the Legend in the Appendix for a full explanation of the acronyms and other terms.

In Figure 4 we provide results for another kind of grouping. We show the results by type of occupation (detailed results are reported in Table A5). Once again, Spanish female employees are subject to more severe discrimination in general, with the exception of the occupational groups that require most skills (managers and professionals). Differences in the distribution of the severity of discrimination between both economies are significant. In Spain discrimination is more severe in low-skilled occupations than in high-skilled ones. Italian data show no such clear distinction, with relatively high values of dr_2 for managers and relatively low values for service and shop employees and elementary occupations.

Figure 1: Values of dr_2 for occupations

Note: see the Legend in the Appendix for a full explanation of the acronyms and other terms.

Hence it is clear that not only the industry, but also occupation matters. To assess further the weight of these factors, and to allow for the different behaviour of the private and the public sector, we build upon the empirical strategy proposed in Arulampalam et al. (2007). We estimate separate wage equations for the public and private sector, and because occupation and industry may be endogenous if individuals choose them based on earning prospects, we also estimate these equations excluding the occupation and industry dummies (the estimation results are omitted for the sake of brevity, and are available upon request). If estimates of the including and omitting controls for occupation and industry are similar, conclusions are robust to the possible endogeneity of occupation and industry and segregation of women into certain occupations and industries is not likely to be a major driver of discrimination.

As a further twist to this strategy, and to provide a robustness check of our results, we calculate the discrimination indexes relying on different non-discriminatory reward structures. Instead of relying on the average male reward structure utilised above, we use male reward structures segmented for sector (public and private) or education level (Primary, Secondary and Tertiary, analogously to glass-ceiling literature). This procedure, akin to the use of local reward structures in the quantile-regression approach, implicitly relies on the hypothesis of a segmented labour market.

In the absence of discrimination, all characteristics (for example a year of tenure or experience) are paid differently depending on the sector or the educational level. Again, the estimation results are omitted for the sake of brevity, and are available upon request.

In order to provide the gist of our results, we adopt a graphical device proposed in Del Rio, et al. (2006) which displays, for index dr_2 , the ratio of within-group discrimination (for each decile) to the overall country mean. A ratio above (below) unity indicates a level of discrimination higher (lower) than that mean.

Let us first consider the non discriminatory rewards segmented by sector, in appraising the two sectors separately.

Figure 1a: dr_2 ratio in the private and public sector using non-discriminatory rewards segmented by sector, controlling for occupation and industry

Figure 5b: dr_2 ratio in the private and public sector using non-discriminatory rewards segmented by sector, without controlling for either occupation or industry

Note: see the Legend in the Appendix for a full explanation of the acronyms and other terms

The contrast between the Italian and Spanish public sectors in both Figures 5a and 5b is very stark and is not influenced by the occupation and industry controls. Using the non-discriminatory rewards segmented by sector, a definite sticky-floor pattern emerges in the Spanish public sector, while the Italian one shows the opposite phenomenon (a glass ceiling). On the other hand, an apparent contrast between the private sectors of the two countries is wiped out by industry and occupation controls. A glass-ceiling pattern always lingers on in the Italian private sector, whereas the sticky floor in the Spanish one seems to be driven by the industry and occupation controls.

Let us now consider the two sectors using non-discriminatory rewards segmented by educational level.

Figure 6a: dr_2 ratio in the private and public sector using non-discriminatory rewards segmented by educational level, controlling for occupation and industry

Figure 6b: dr_2 ratio in the private and public sector using non-discriminatory rewards segmented by educational level, without controlling for either occupation or industry

Note: see the Legend in the Appendix for a full explanation of the acronyms and other terms

A robust and well-defined glass-ceiling pattern shows up again in Figures 6a and 6b for Italy, especially in the public sector. This once more differs from the pattern in the Spanish public sector. The impact of industry and occupation controls is

qualitatively heavier in Spain (where a glass-ceiling effect in the private sector basically disappears after one controls for activity and occupation), and in the private sector. Differently from what happened in the previous case (non-discriminatory rewards segmented by sector), there is some evidence of contrasting behaviour in the Italian and Spanish private sectors, once industry and occupation controls are taken into account.

At any rate it appears from both Figures 5 and 6 that, in Spain much more than in Italy, the glass-ceiling and sticky-floor patterns found in the literature very much depend upon industry and occupation considerations. In order to finesse our understanding, we follow upon the practice, suggested by De la Rica et al. (2008), to focus separately on different educational levels. Figures 7 and 8, shown below, basically reiterate the analysis of Figures 5 and 6, but three educational levels (primary, secondary and tertiary) are considered separately.

Figure 7a: dr_2 ratio in the public and private sectors, three educational levels, using non-discriminatory rewards segmented by sector, controlling for occupation and industry

Note: see the Legend in the Appendix for a full explanation of the acronyms and other terms.

Figure 7b: dr_2 ratio in the public and private sectors, three educational levels, using non-discriminatory rewards segmented by sector, without controlling for either occupation or industry

Note: see the Legend in the Appendix for a full explanation of the acronyms and other terms.

Figure 8a: dr_2 ratio in the public and private sectors, three educational levels, using non-discriminatory rewards segmented by educational level, controlling for occupation and industry

Note: see the Legend in the Appendix for a full explanation of the acronyms and other terms.

Figure 8b: dr_2 ratio in the public and private sectors, three educational levels, using non-discriminatory rewards segmented by educational level, without controlling for either occupation or industry

Note: see the Legend in the Appendix for a full explanation of the acronyms and other terms.

Figures 7 and 8 provide a clear, and rather striking, configuration of the glass-ceiling pattern of the Italian public sector. Under both hypotheses about the non-discriminatory reward structure, wage discrimination is much higher for university-educated Italian women working in the public sector, than for any other cut of the data

(obviously including university-educated Spanish women working in the public sector). The existence of some glass-ceiling effect in the Italian private is not equally robust to hypotheses about the non discriminatory reward structure and to controlling for industry and occupation.

These results clearly that some mechanism inhibiting the access of highly educated women to highly rewarding occupations is working in Italy, especially in the public sector, but not in Spain. The justifications for this glass-ceiling phenomenon based on the arguments by Lazear and Rosen (1990) or Albrecht et al. (2003), although may to some extent explain the differences between Italy and Spain, are not likely to satisfactorily explain the differences between the public and private sectors in the two countries. Another explanation related to the taste-based argument, i.e. that relatively high wages at the bottom of the wage distribution make it relatively difficult for career-oriented women to hire household or childcare help, is equally unsatisfactory: the relative gap between wages for educated women from the private or the public sector and women with primary education in the private sector (a rough proxy for the wages of household or childcare help) is basically the same in the two countries. Other factors are also likely to be at work.

At this juncture, it should be noted that, unfortunately, the ECHP contains no information about individual union membership or coverage by collective bargaining. At any rate, labour markets are usually hierarchical: exactly where in the rank-specific salary scale a successful candidate is appointed can depend on individual negotiation and hence on discrimination. Furthermore, a glass ceiling may come into existence if promotions favour men rather than women. There is for instance evidence from the UK academic economists' labour market (Blackaby et al., 2005), that promotions might exacerbate gender pay inequality if men have more outside offers. A similar mechanism may be at work in our case. Whereas in 1998 the gap between highly educated female and male unemployment rates was, respectively for Spain and Italy, of 12.1 and 4.8 percentage points, in 2001 it had decreased to 6.9 in Spain, but only to 3.8 in Italy (this trend has gone further. In 2008 the gaps were equal to 2.5 in both countries). It thus appears that the market for highly educated females was considerably more buoyant in Spain than in Italy. We can only make an informed guess why this should regard more the public than the private sector. Spain adopted in March 2007 a gender equality law, including notably gender quotas for medium- to high-skilled employment in the public

sector, and more generally fostering promotion equality plans. In some Spanish regions (Comunidades Autonomas) similar laws already existed before, and a powerful political pressure along these lines had long been in place all across the country (Papavero, 2007). Nothing of the kind exists in Italy, highlighting a remarkable institutional divide between the two countries in this domain.

Concluding Remarks

In this paper we have attempted to show that when comparing gender wage discrimination among different countries it is not enough to look at aggregate levels of degrees of discrimination. If information is available, it is worth to search for ways to compare the entire distributions. To this end we have computed individual indexes of gender wage discrimination for Italy and Spain. Then, relying on the decomposability properties of these indexes, these discrimination measures are aggregated across various socio-economic groupings, allowing us to assess empirically the nature and extent of discrimination across these groups. Moreover, various hypotheses have been made about the non-discriminatory reward structure.

Italian and Spanish labour markets share some general similarities as fulfilling some Southern European stereotypes, and their aggregate measures of discrimination (according to ECHP data) fall within a narrow range. However, our analysis reveals significant differences in the distribution of the Italian and Spanish individual measures of discrimination. In particular, we find that some mechanisms inhibit the access of highly educated women to highly rewarding occupations in Italy, especially in the public sector, but not in Spain. The relevance of the sector of activity, especially insofar as the public-private divide is concerned, also sheds some doubts on the robustness of the results obtained by De la Rica et al. (2008) and in the related literature. These results point to the operation of different discriminating mechanisms in the two labour markets. While no doubt this point will gain extensively from further research, we have pointed out some prima-facie evidence for appointment and promotion schemes as relevant factors in this respect.

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Appendix

Table A- 1: Descriptive statistics (mean)

	Italy		Spain	
	Women	Men	Women	Men
MARITAL STATUS				
married	0.63	0.69	0.48	0.63
Non-married	0.37	0.31	0.52	0.37
EXPERIENCE				
Less than 5 years	0.15	0.12	0.22	0.12
5 to 9 years	0.15	0.11	0.16	0.11
10 to 19 years	0.31	0.26	0.29	0.26
20 to 29 years	0.26	0.30	0.20	0.25
30 to 39 years	0.12	0.17	0.11	0.17
More than 40 years	0.02	0.04	0.03	0.08
TENURE				
Less than 2 years	0.18	0.18	0.40	0.34
2 to 4 years	0.16	0.15	0.17	0.17
5 to 9 years	0.17	0.15	0.15	0.11
More than 10 years	0.50	0.52	0.28	0.38
EXPERIENCE SQUARE	396.14	512.64	361.46	574.59
TENURE SQUARE	160.69	172.55	90.48	122.50
EDUCATION				
Tertiary (ISCED 5-7)	0.13	0.12	0.43	0.29
Secondary (ISCED 3)	0.55	0.42	0.22	0.19
Primary (ISCED 0-2)	0.32	0.46	0.34	0.51
OCUPATION				
Legislators	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.04
Professionals	0.17	0.07	0.22	0.11
Technicians	0.12	0.11	0.13	0.11
Clerks	0.34	0.20	0.18	0.07
Service	0.12	0.09	0.20	0.09
Skill	0.10	0.26	0.05	0.29
Operators	0.05	0.13	0.03	0.14
Elementary	0.10	0.10	0.18	0.14
TYPE OF CONTRACT				
Indefinite contract	0.88	0.89	0.64	0.68
Fixed term contract	0.12	0.11	0.36	0.32
JOB STATUS				
Full time	0.89	0.99	0.87	0.98
Part time	0.11	0.01	0.13	0.02
FIRM SIZE				
0 to 4 employees	0.20	0.18	0.21	0.15
5 to 19 employees	0.28	0.27	0.22	0.28
20 to 49 employees	0.18	0.17	0.17	0.18
50 to 99 employees	0.11	0.10	0.11	0.10
100 to 499 employees	0.14	0.16	0.14	0.15
More than 500 employees	0.09	0.13	0.15	0.14

Table A1: Descriptive statistics (mean) (continuation)

	Italy		Spain	
	Women	Men	Women	Men
INDUSTRY				
a+b+c+e	0.03	0.07	0.02	0.07
d	0.21	0.30	0.15	0.25
f	0.01	0.08	0.01	0.17
g-k	0.26	0.26	0.37	0.32
l+n	0.23	0.18	0.22	0.10
m	0.19	0.05	0.13	0.05
o-q	0.08	0.06	0.10	0.04
YEAR				
1997	0.22	0.22	0.19	0.21
1998	0.21	0.21	0.20	0.20
1999	0.20	0.20	0.19	0.20
2000	0.19	0.19	0.20	0.20
2001	0.18	0.17	0.21	0.20
<i>Number of obser-</i> <i>ventions</i>	7488	11441	7206	12505

Table A- 2: Estimation results

	Italy		Spain	
	Women	Men	Women	Men
MARITAL STATUS				
Married	0.02*	0.08***	0.03*	0.07***
	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
Non-married	<i>Reference</i>		<i>Reference</i>	
EXPERIENCE				
Less than 5 years	-0.15***	-0.20***	-0.20***	-0.23***
	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.03
5 to 9 years	-0.05*	-0.15***	-0.09**	-0.12***
	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.02
10 to 19 years	-0.00	-0.04**	-0.07**	-0.07***
	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.02
20 to 29 years	<i>Reference</i>		<i>Reference</i>	
30 to 39 years	0.02	0.02	-0.02	0.04*
	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.02
More than 40 years	-0.03	-0.02	-0.07	0.04
	0.05	0.04	0.06	0.04
TENURE				
Less than 2 years	-0.01	-0.03*	-0.14***	-0.05**
	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02
2 and 4 years	-0.01	-0.04**	-0.06*	-0.02
	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02
5 and 9 years	<i>Reference</i>		<i>Reference</i>	
More than 10 years	0.01	-0.01	0.03	0.01
	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.02
EXPERIENCE SQUARE				
	-0.00	-0.00	0.00	-0.00
	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
TENURE SQUARE				
	0.00***	0.00***	0.00***	0.00***
	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
EDUCATION				
Tertiary (ISCED 5-7)	0.20***	0.24***	0.05**	0.13***
	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02
Secondary (ISCED 3)	<i>Reference</i>		<i>Reference</i>	
Primary (ISCED 0-2)	-0.08***	-0.08***	-0.11***	-0.10***
	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
OCUPATION				
Legislators	0.59***	0.56***	0.89***	0.71***
	0.09	0.03	0.08	0.03
Professionals	0.37***	0.32***	0.62***	0.44***
	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.03
Technicians	0.22***	0.16***	0.35***	0.24***
	0.02	0.01	0.03	0.02
Clerks	0.16***	0.12***	0.20***	0.21***
	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.02
Service	0.06***	0.03**	0.06*	-0.02
	0.02	0.01	0.03	0.02
Skill	<i>Reference</i>		<i>Reference</i>	
Operators	0.05**	0.04***	0.05	-0.00
	0.02	0.01	0.04	0.01
Elementary	0.02	-0.04***	0.00	-0.08***
	0.02	0.01	0.03	0.01

Table A2: Estimation results (continuation)

	Italy		Spain	
	Women	Men	Women	Men
TYPE OF CONTRACT				
Indefinite contract	0.10*** 0.02	0.11*** 0.01	0.13*** 0.01	0.15*** 0.01
Fixed term contract	<i>Reference</i>		<i>Reference</i>	
JOB STATUS				
Full time	<i>Reference</i>		<i>Reference</i>	
Part time	0.17*** 0.01	0.13*** 0.03	0.14*** 0.02	0.18*** 0.04
FIRM SIZE				
Between 1 and 4 employees	-0.08*** 0.01	-0.06*** 0.01	-0.06*** 0.02	-0.06*** 0.01
Between 5 and 19 employees	<i>Reference</i>		<i>Reference</i>	
Between 20 and 49 employees	0.05*** 0.01	0.07*** 0.01	0.10*** 0.02	0.08*** 0.01
Between 50 and 99 employees	0.09*** 0.01	0.10*** 0.01	0.15*** 0.02	0.13*** 0.01
Between 100 and 499 employees	0.06*** 0.01	0.10*** 0.01	0.18*** 0.02	0.23*** 0.01
More than 500 employees	0.12*** 0.01	0.12*** 0.01	0.18*** 0.02	0.27*** 0.01
INDUSTRY				
a+b+c+e	-0.11*** 0.03	-0.06*** 0.02	-0.07* 0.04	-0.04 0.02
d	-0.05*** 0.01	-0.05*** 0.01	-0.04 0.02	0.04** 0.01
f	-0.04 0.04	0.00 0.01	0.01 0.05	0.13*** 0.01
g-k	<i>Reference</i>		<i>Reference</i>	
l+n	0.01 0.01	-0.06*** 0.01	-0.02 0.01	-0.03 0.01
m	0.11*** 0.02	0.07*** 0.02	0.09*** 0.02	0.05 0.03
o-q	-0.04** 0.02	-0.05** 0.02	-0.11*** 0.02	-0.01 0.04
YEAR				
1997	-0.12*** 0.01	-0.11*** 0.01	-0.12*** 0.01	-0.12*** 0.01
1998	-0.05*** 0.01	-0.05*** 0.01	-0.06*** 0.02	-0.06*** 0.01
1999	<i>Reference</i>		<i>Reference</i>	
2000	0.05*** 0.01	0.05*** 0.01	0.08*** 0.02	0.08*** 0.01
2001	0.09*** 0.01	0.09*** 0.01	0.14*** 0.02	0.15*** 0.01
Constant	2.26*** 0.03	2.42*** 0.03	6.39*** 0.05	6.51*** 0.03
<i>Number of observations</i>	7488	11441	7206	12505
<i>Adjusted R-Square</i>	0.55	0.53	0.66	0.61

* p<0.05; ** p<0.01; *** p<0.001

Table A- 3: Discrimination indexes for educational levels

	Italy			Spain		
	dr ₀	dr ₁	dr ₂	dr ₀	dr ₁	dr ₂
Primary (ISCED 0-2)	98.77%	13.12%	2.01%	99.68%	16.86%	3.29%
Secondary (ISCED 3)	95.65%	10.05%	1.26%	97.76%	14.88%	2.74%
Tertiary (ISCED 5-7)	99.44%	12.07%	1.65%	91.62%	13.84%	2.76%

Table A- 4: Discrimination indexes for industry

	Italy			Spain		
	dr ₀	dr ₁	dr ₂	dr ₀	dr ₁	dr ₂
a+b+c+e	100.00%	16.98%	3.05%	100.00%	18.43%	3.72%
d	99.85%	13.43%	2.09%	100.00%	21.83%	5.10%
f	100.00%	15.50%	2.51%	100.00%	24.25%	6.36%
g-k	99.35%	12.21%	1.72%	99.23%	14.45%	2.51%
l+n	91.24%	7.79%	0.80%	98.01%	14.10%	2.47%
m	97.38%	10.85%	1.39%	73.05%	4.79%	0.55%
o-q	98.07%	11.41%	1.51%	100.00%	21.46%	4.89%

Table A- 5: Discrimination indexes for occupations

	Italy			Spain		
	dr ₀	dr ₁	dr ₂	dr ₀	dr ₁	dr ₂
Legislators	99.36%	14.48%	2.27%	82.00%	7.73%	1.01%
Profession- als	96.64%	10.80%	1.38%	82.19%	6.75%	0.80%
Technicians	90.59%	7.68%	0.81%	99.30%	14.22%	2.38%
Clerks	98.31%	11.62%	1.58%	100.00%	23.26%	5.70%
Service	98.07%	11.17%	1.47%	100.00%	14.12%	2.30%
Skill	100.00%	15.75%	2.74%	100.00%	24.44%	6.15%
Operators	99.72%	14.54%	2.36%	100.00%	21.51%	4.83%
Elementary	97.02%	9.71%	1.20%	99.50%	15.55%	2.80%

Table A- 6: Values of γ

EDUCATION	
Primary (ISCED 0-2)	-0.01
Secondary (ISCED 3)	-0.02
Tertiary (ISCED 5-7)	0.35
INDUSTRY	
a+b+c+e	0.04
d	-0.21
f	0.08
g-k	0.06
l+n	-0.20
m	0.20
o-q	-0.30
OCCUPATIONS	
Legislators	0.16
Professionals	0.18
Technicians	-0.50
Clerks	-0.41
Service	-0.04
Skill	-0.16
Operators	-0.14
Elementary	-0.24

Legend**EDUCA-
TION**

Primary	Pre-primary education, primary education and lower secondary education (ISCED 0-2)
Secondary	Upper secondary education (ISCED 3)
Tertiary	First and second stage of tertiary education (ISCED 5-7)

INDUSTRY

a+b+c+e	Agriculture, hunting and forestry Fishing Mining and quarrying Electricity, gas and water supply
d	Manufacturing
f	Construction
g-k	Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles, motorcycles and personal and household goods Hotels and restaurants Transport, storage and communication Financial intermediation Real estate, renting and business activities
l+n	Public administration and defence; compulsory social security Health and social work
m	Education
o-q	Other community, social and personal service activities Activities of households Extra-territorial organizations and bodies

OCCUPATION

Legislators	Legislators, senior officials and managers
Professionals	Professionals
Technicians	Technicians and associate professionals
Clerks	Clerks
Service	Service workers and shop and market sales workers
Skill	Skilled workers
Operators	Plant and machine operators and assemblers
Elementary	Elementary occupations
